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1 Executive Summary

This report describes the work done in the NextGenProteins project on the subject ‘how to boost consumer trust and acceptance for alternative proteins?’ The work combines perspectives from research and business.

Trust is not a major obstacle for the consumer acceptance of food products including alternative proteins, according to the work carried out in the project. Therefore, the recommendations are focused on other actions.

The report proposes the following recommendations:

Products must be price competitive

Pricing of food products including alternative protein ingredients needs to be competitively set against conventional proteins to encourage trial and subsequently build acceptance. Preferably the price should be lower than corresponding product with animal protein. If this is not the case, the product must bring additional benefit to the customer.

Promote sustainability

Consumers are increasingly aware of the impact of their food choices on the environment. This awareness can be used as an opportunity by feeding correct information on the sustainability of food products including alternative proteins.

Promote food products

Promotion of alternative protein products should be actively used to attract consumers towards new food products. This would include tastings in supermarkets, introductory offers, etc.

Continue development of products

Ideally, range and choice of food products should be as wide as possible to meet the varied preferences of consumers. Food companies should continue the development of new food products including alternative proteins. Part of the new products should go beyond typical categories of meat alternatives to attract consumers that are omnivore but who are suspicious of meat alternatives. In addition to increasing the range of products, the food development should focus on decreasing the number of E-labels in products, keeping in mind the importance of taste and other sensory properties in the acceptance of new products.

Marketing through social media influencers

Marketing of alternative protein food products should take place through influencers in social media, because the most potential users of alternative protein food products are active in social media. Currently Instagram and TikTok are the platforms through which the target groups could best be reached. The marketing should underline the value of products.

2 Introduction

Global food protein consumption is in high increase due to growing population and socio-demographics changes such as urbanisation, increased income, and recognition of proteins' role in healthy diets (Henchion et al. 2017; de Boer & Aiking, 2019; UN, 2022). It is, therefore, of vital importance to find protein sources that could be produced sustainably in quantities meeting the growing demand. Business actors in the food and feed value chain are largely aware about the sustainability needs of food production. They are searching for sustainable practices for the existing ones and are ready to apply them, when consumers are willing to go for sustainable products. Business actors also require that new solutions are sustainable not only environmentally but also economically (Paasi et al. 2021). Alternative proteins such as plants, algae, insects, micro-organisms, or cultured meat are considered promising for decreasing the burden of protein consumption to the environment and health (Geada et al., 2021; Grossman & Weiss, 2021). Perceptions of consumers towards foods including these alternative proteins have been studied by several research groups (see e.g., Onwezen et al., 2021, and references therein). According to these studies, consumer acceptance of the alternative proteins is relatively low, compared to meat. However, there are differences in consumer perceptions between individuals and between alternative proteins, as shown by Onwezen et al. (2021). It is, therefore, important to boost consumer acceptance and trust towards alternative proteins in foods, to enhance the use of sustainable proteins in foods.

One of the objectives of NextGenProteins project and its WP5 'Market opportunities and business potential' was to identify suitable approaches to boost consumer trust and acceptability towards alternative protein sources and processes. Special attention was paid to the three alternative protein concepts under consideration in the NextGenProteins project for food applications: Spirulina (a microalgae), House Cricket (an edible insect), and Torula yeast (a single-cell protein). This report is the summary of work done on the subject. It combines perspectives from research and business, and it is structured as follows: methods and materials used in the study are summarized in chapters 3 and 4, respectively, actual results are presented and discussed in chapter 5, and, finally, main recommendations to boost consumer acceptance towards alternative proteins are given in chapter 6.

3 Methods

A multi-method approach was applied in the research where findings from other research done in the NextGenProteins project were combined with findings from literature and the insights and experience of two business actors in the project: Waitrose Limited, a major UK retailer, and Peas of Heaven, a food company located in Sweden and focused on plant-based meat alternative products.

The NextGenProteins research used as an input included studies done in:

- Task 5.1 ‘Market opportunities for novel products containing alternative proteins’ on consumer attitudes towards alternative proteins, including focus group discussions and a large European consumer survey,
- WP3 ‘Alternative protein application in concept food products’ including findings from consumers tests done for food prototypes developed,
- WP1 ‘Regulations, safety and legal requirements’ especially on food safety related aspects,
- WP6 ‘Sustainability assessment’.

Further detail on the material that was used in the study can be found in the following chapter, Materials.

Waitrose insights were derived from a variety of sources: 1. consumer analysis on how samples of farmed Atlantic salmon reared on the novel proteins performed against a control sample (as a part of WP 4 ‘Alternative protein application in feed products’ work). 2. paid reports from Mintel market intelligence and research agency, and 3. internal expertise and experience from the retailer’s Commercial teams, New Product Development Teams, Sustainability and Ethics teams, and Marketing Teams.

Peas of Heaven insights were based on their experience in Swedish food markets and their work in WP3 of the project.

The research question of the study is: **how to boost consumer trust and acceptance for alternative proteins** and, especially, for the three concepts considered in the project? The aim was to identify methods with the most impact for the boosting. The selection for the main recommendations in chapter 6 was done in a workshop by the authors comprising both business and research perspectives on the subject.

4 Material (Input for the study)

4.1 NextGenProteins consumer survey

In order to gain a European view on consumer attitudes towards the three NextGenProteins protein sources (Spirulina, House crickets and Torula yeast), their production processes, and the use of resulting protein ingredients in food products, a large online survey was carried out in the project. The study was conducted in seven European countries (United Kingdom, Finland, Italy, Sweden, Poland, Germany, and Iceland) in 2021 with a total sample size of 6,640 consumers. Details of the survey have been presented elsewhere (Arvola et al, 2021; Matullat et. al. 2023). Below is a summary of the main findings.

The survey study focused on segmentation of European consumers from seven different countries according to the consumers perceptions of the three different alternative protein concepts (Spirulina, House crickets and Torula yeast). The study identified four consumer segments for each alternative protein type, i.e., highly positive, reservedly positive, neutral and negative. For all protein sources, neutral consumers with neither strongly positive nor negative perceptions formed the largest segment. For Spirulina and Torula yeast, the share of positive-minded consumers was larger than for the House crickets. In the Spirulina case, the share of those having positive views exceeded 50 % of the sample, for Torula the number was approximately 43 %, while for House crickets the number decreased to about 20 %.

The results of the study were to some extent aligned with earlier findings in the literature. In general, insect protein was found less interesting to consumers than other alternative sources such as plant-based alternatives or microalgae (Takeda et al., 2023). However, the results of the study show that the overall share (above 60 %) of neutral or positive consumers was relatively high in House cricket case as well, although earlier studies often report low consumer acceptance for insects (e.g. Grasso et al., 2019). This result might be explained by the general positive attitudinal change towards the alternative proteins and products made of them among European consumers (Aschemann-Witzel & Janssen, 2022). Further, it has been found that informing consumers about the benefits of insect-based alternative proteins (as was the case here) tends to have positive influence on their attitudes (Dagevos & Taufik, 2023; Michel & Begho, 2023).

Taken together, the study reports relatively high acceptance numbers for all Spirulina and Torula and moderately positive for House crickets. However, it must be kept in mind that despite the positive perceptions and attitudes, the alternative proteins have not found their way to consumers' plates as indicated by the recent market numbers (Statista, 2022). When the identified segments are studied more closely, it can be seen that the positive segments can be divided into two in the Spirulina and Torula case; highly positive and reservedly positive. From these two positive segments, the highly positive, who represented about 18 % of Spirulina sample and 12 % of Torula sample, seem very promising as they show very high attitudes, benefits, food views and very low risks concerning the protein sources.

The study also aimed to predict segment classification through various demographic, socio-economic, psychographic and external environment variables. Being a younger male predicted membership of those segments who held negative perception towards all studied alternative proteins. In general, younger age also predicted the membership of positive segments, indicating that younger consumers are more open to alternative proteins (but also

less open in some cases). These findings are well in line with earlier studies (Onwezen et al., 2021). Interestingly, the level of education did not predict any of the segment classification, although highly educated consumers are often found to be more open to alternative proteins (Onwezen et al., 2021). Possibly this is a matter of the questionnaire design. The education level was evaluated based on seven different education classes. It became obvious during the analysis, that those classes are difficult to compare across Europe and resulted in the formation of the simple binary variable. This type of data condensation could have had a major impact on the results.

Psychographic variables predicted segment memberships more or less in a way described in earlier studies. Higher meat attachment was predicting membership of the negative segments (and vice versa) (cf. Michel et al., 2021), positive attitude towards food technologies predicted being a member of positive segments (and vice versa) (cf. Krings, Dhont, & Hodson, 2022), higher tendency to avoid novel foods was a character for those belonging to the negative segments (and vice versa) (cf. Siegrist & Hartmann, 2020), and higher trust in food chain increased the odds of belonging to the positive segments (and vice versa) (cf. Siegrist & Hartmann, 2020). Food domain innovativeness did not have a role in predicting negative segment memberships, but in most of the cases it predicted positive segment membership. Earlier studies have found that resistance to novelty does not necessarily correlate with lower food acceptance (e.g. Bartels & Reinders, 2010). This might explain the study results; lack of innovativeness in the food domain would not necessarily mean that consumers would be negative towards food alternative proteins.

The predictive role of the three food choice motives (taste, health, and environment and ethics) was analysed. In general, the results related to taste motive were as expected based on earlier literature (e.g. de Boer et al., 2013). Higher importance of the motive predicted the negative segment membership, while the motive did not have a predictive role (negative or positive) in terms of the positive segments. This also indicates that the taste motive might not be the top priority for those who already perceive alternative proteins positively. Higher health motive was connected with the positive Spirulina segments. In terms of House crickets, health motive did not predict membership of any segments while in Torula higher health motive positively predicted each segments' membership. The Spirulina results might be explained by the familiarity of the ingredient and its inherent association with healthiness, as it has been on the market as a food supplement for a long time. The results related to House crickets are in line with earlier research (e.g. Grasso et al., 2019). Health motive is not driving the attitudes or intentions towards insects, even if the nutritional value was emphasised in the study. The results related to Torula were interesting as the elevated health motive predicted membership of both positive and negative segments. It might be that Torula is such an unfamiliar ingredient to consumers that it produces mixed associations. Those who have positive view believe in its health benefits while those who have negative view might consider that avoidance of the ingredient was beneficial from health perspective. Finally, elevated food choice motive related to environment and ethics predicted the membership of positive segments in all ingredients. This is in line with earlier findings (e.g. Niva & Vainio, 2021; Nguyen et al., 2022) although in some studies such connection has not been found in terms of insects (Grasso et al., 2019). Lower motive in environment and ethics predicted negative segment membership in the case of Spirulina and Torula. In House crickets similar result were not found. This indicated that those who are negative towards House crickets do not base their decision on personal sustainability and ethics motives but rather on other issues.

In most of the cases, higher familiarity with current alternative proteins and future alternative proteins predicted being a member of a segment, which has positive view on the studied alternative proteins (and vice versa). This finding was in line with earlier studies emphasising the importance of alternative protein familiarity to consumers (Nezlek & Forestell, 2022). Overall, when observing the regression coefficients, indeed the familiarity was among the strongest predictors.

The study included seven European countries, thus country-wise differences deserve some discussion. The overall view on the results indicated that no major differences exist between the countries. However, Italy as a representative of Southern Europe caused some variation in all studied alternative proteins. There were fewer Italians in consumer segments with positive perspectives and more in segments with negative perspectives. In their review, Mancini and Antonioli (2022) described several articles dealing with the insect acceptance. For example, the rejection of insects as food in Italy seemed to be justified by the deep-rooted tradition of Italian food, which leads to a strong expression of neophobia towards novelties. However, this issue might not be restricted to Italy only. Ribeiro et al. (2022) compared the acceptance of insects in food and feed between Norway and Portugal. Their study also showed that consumers from the Mediterranean habitat were more likely to reject insects than consumers from Norway.

In the case of Torula, Swedish consumers showed similar tendency as the Italians. For Swedish consumers, the reason for this can only be speculated. Swedish consumer studies on use of alternative proteins and meat alternatives have shown that there are consumption barriers related to taste, familiarity, and overall attractiveness (Röös et al, 2022). In addition, Spendrup & Hovmalm, (2022) found that the ready-to-eat processed plant-based meat alternatives were perceived as modern, artificial and expensive by the Swedes. Perhaps the Swedish participants in our study perceived the Torula yeast concept too abstract, artificial and highly processed, increasing the odds of being a negative segment member instead of the positive one.

Finally, being a German or Polish predicted optimistic perspective towards House crickets. This is interesting as to the authors' knowledge there are no compelling evidence that German and Polish consumers would be more interested in insect than the consumers in other European countries. In contrary, many studies in both countries have highlighted that neither Polish nor German consumers are very open to insect consumption. For instance, Orsi et al. (2019) found a low willingness among German participants to try insects mainly due to disgust and food neophobia. In a Polish study, Kostecka, Konieczna, and Cunha (2017) reported similar results in Germany as Orsi et al. (2019). However, they found that Polish consumers appreciated that the food industry uses natural resources respectfully and further speculated that informing consumers about the benefits of insects to reduce the burden to nature could be beneficial in alleviating the negative attitude towards the insects. Perhaps, in our study case the information provided about the insect cultivation could have had stronger positive effect on Polish and German consumers resulting in the country effect predicting the positive segment membership.

4.2 NextGenProteins consumer testing of food products

4.2.1 Testing of food prototypes

WP3 of the project consisted of concept food development in four food categories: ready meals, bakery products, imitation meat, and advanced functional food supplements, all containing the NextGenProteins alternative proteins as ingredients. The research included consumer testing in each category. The results are confidential, but here below is a summary of findings from the consumer tests.

Sensory properties (taste, texture, appearance, flavour, etc.) were found to be highly important for the consumer acceptance of food products; sustainability is not enough. The taste was found to be especially important. At the same time, it is important to keep in mind that sensorial preferences are personal. While somebody likes umami taste, others may dislike it. Most of the consumers, however, found food products among the tested products that they liked.

The willingness to buy the products was, however, rather low among the consumers participating in the tests (the assumption was that the tested products would be in available on markets). The findings are in line with the findings of the consumer survey that the overall positive attitudes of European consumers towards alternative proteins do not directly turn to a personal interest to buy products containing these new proteins (Arvola et al. 2021). The WP3 studies show first importance of products price and, secondly, the willingness to buy vegetarian or vegan food products. Most consumers were not willing to pay a premium for products containing alternative protein ingredients. However, country specific perceptions were identified, for example consumers in Germany were more reluctant to pay a premium for alternative proteins compared with consumers in Iceland. It should be pointed out that the willingness to pay was surveyed solely on the basis of sensory properties. In addition to the intrinsic properties, extrinsic properties such as packaging and product descriptions have an impact on the product's success and on willingness to pay. The other reason, why the quite positive overall attitude towards alternative protein in food products may not turn to personal interest to buy such products, is related to unfamiliarity or general disliking of vegetarian meals by many consumers.

The NextGenProteins finding that consumers are not willing to pay premium for products containing alternative proteins is not in line with earlier results of consumer survey by Kerry (Leveille & Nair, 2021). They found that a large majority of European consumers are willing to pay 5-10% premium for protein-fortified options. The discrepancy of the findings could be explained by time factor in carrying out the surveys. The data for the Kerry survey was collected in 2021 while the data for the NextGenProteins WP3 studies in 2023, when geopolitical and economic situations in Europe were very different to that in 2021.

4.2.2 Testing of Atlantic salmon

As a part of WP4 work, Waitrose innovation centre conducted a consumer analysis on how samples of farmed Atlantic salmon reared on the novel proteins (all at 10% inclusion) performed against a control sample, see Rubio et al. (2023) for detailed results. The 80 participants in the consumer analysis shop at Waitrose were subject to a controlled blind acceptance test of raw and cooked product to assess the level of liking, satisfaction with key sensory attributes and purchase intent.

There were no significant differences in consumer satisfaction on appearance and odour for the raw or cooked samples but there was (5%) in the cooked products for flavour, texture, mouthfeel and overall liking. The single cell protein consistently scored the highest (in parallel with the control) and in the strength of flavour, alongside insect meal, they outperformed the control. Comparatively the algal protein consistently scored the lowest. Interestingly Algal oil is already used in many farmed salmon feeds with negligible or no differences in customer satisfaction: this indicates that the proteins behave differently (comparative trials are needed to validate this) and that there is good potential for the single cell protein to be considered for salmon feeds, and this may have potential to extend to other finfish and livestock feeds. This is because regardless of LCA results, the most important factor for retail food sales is the quality (which includes taste) of the final product.

4.3 NextGenProteins regulatory and sustainability studies

4.3.1 EU food regulative framework

EU regulates the conditions for the actors of food value chain to produce and commercialise their products in the European Union. General principles and standards in the area of food and feed safety are given in the 'General Food Law' (Regulation No 178/2002) and the 'Hygiene Package' (e.g. Regulation No 853/2004 on the hygiene of foodstuffs and Regulation No 1831/2003 laying down requirements for feed hygiene). According to these legislative texts, actors of food value chain are responsible for ensuring the safety of the marketed products. Among other things, these texts specify general obligations on the actors to the registration or approval of their activities and to establish hygiene standards to be applied at the different stages of food production.

The novel foods regulation (Regulation EU 2015/2283) was set to guarantee the safety of new food products. The aim of the novel foods regulation is to improve conditions so that the food industry can bring new, innovative and safe foods to the EU market. Authorization is needed before entering markets for any novel "food that had not been consumed to a significant degree by humans in the EU before 15th May 1997".

From the viewpoint of consumers, the European food regulation provides mechanisms to increase consumer confidence and trust. Consumers can expect that only safe food and feed can be placed on the market or fed to food-producing animals. The regulation also sets the rule that tracing of food and feed throughout the food chain is compulsory. Traceability provides ability to track any item that will be used for consumption, throughout all stages of production, processing and distribution.

Regarding the alternative proteins studied in the NextGenProteins project for food applications, all are accepted for the use in foods in the EU. See NextGenProteins Deliverable 1.1 "Documentation on EU legal/regulatory landscape and the safety of alternative proteins for food" (Alakomi et al., 2020) and Deliverable 1.3 "Policy recommendations" (Agnarsson et al., 2023) for more details on food regulation and the safety of foods including alternative protein ingredients.

4.3.2 Sustainability framework

Global protein consumption has been growing for a long time, not only due to the population increase but also due to the increase as measured as grams per capita. This latter increase is mostly due to a vastly increased consumption of animal-based proteins (FAOSTAT, 2023). Agriculture and land use are major sources of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. It has been estimated that GHG emissions from food systems account for 35% of global total anthropogenic GHG emissions (Xu et al., 2021). Over half of that comes from the production of animal-based food (including livestock feed), and around 30% from the production of plant-based foods. Agriculture is also responsible for 70% of global freshwater withdrawals. Current dominant practices in agriculture and aquaculture constitute a major threat to biodiversity. Increase of protein production for food and feed using conventional practices can, therefore, not be done without toll in sustainability. This is a major driver for the development and implementation of alternative proteins in food and feed.

Production of alternative proteins, however, is not automatically more sustainable if compared to conventional ways of food production. Sustainability of production is highly dependent on the used technology and process. Therefore, the sustainability of any new protein concept should be scientifically proven if one is aiming to use sustainability as a marketing argument of the protein ingredient. Unfortunately, this has not always been done. False argumentation on sustainability may end in “green washing” of consumers, diminishing their trust in food operators and lowering consumer acceptance towards alternative proteins.

When considering the sustainability of protein ingredient production, one should consider circularity, resource efficiency and GHG emissions of the food system in question throughout the whole life cycle (LCA, life-cycle assessment). For the alternative proteins specifically considered in the NextGenProteins project, such studies have been reported in Deliverable 6.3 “Report on circular economy potential of alternative proteins” (Agnarsson et al, 2022).

4.4 Sustainability and alternative proteins in food: case UK

In the UK, many people, though not the majority (48%), feel a pressure to live more sustainably (Mintel, 2022). There is also a strong feeling among consumers that eating less meat is better for the environment, with 41% of people holding this view (Mintel, 2023). In the UK meat substitute products are gaining traction, with over a quarter of the population (26%) eating meat substitute products once a week (Mintel 2022). However, the majority of UK consumers believe there are better ways to mitigate their environmental impact than reducing this meat intake (Mintel 2022). Many consumers are eating an increasingly plant based diet but do not classify themselves as vegetarian or vegan, but rather choose to include more plants in their diet. Retailers, including Waitrose, are offering more ‘flexitarian’ ranges (substituting a portion of meat for plant ingredients) such as sausages with pepper, tomato and butter beans: these sit alongside traditional meat ranges rather than with the meat substitute ranges.

It is not appropriate to simply substitute a protein. It must be justifiable to the consumer: providing a lower environmental impact, better nutrition, competitive price are examples which may sway a consumer.

Macronutrients go through phases of demonisation and promotion, and currently protein is a favoured nutrient amongst some consumers, particularly those who are trying to reduce

their carbohydrates. This provides an opportunity for the alternative proteins in foods: to target those who are focusing on a high protein diet.

4.5 Increasing interest towards plant-based products: case Sweden

The brand Peas of Heaven (PoH) launched its first products in 2018. During that time, pea protein has only been widely available for 2 years. The launch of the Beyond Burger in 2016 has increased the attention and popularity of pea protein. Now, 5 years later, POH has experienced how the consumer acceptance towards new plant-based protein sources has changed.

During the NextGenProteins project, PoHs focus was on yeast protein combined with pea protein. A lot of arguments for and against new protein sources apply to both, yeast and pea protein to a similar extent. Overall, the acceptance towards vegan protein sources has risen in recent years, which occurred due to different reasons. Apart from ethical reasons, new (plant-based) protein sources have similar nutritional values compared to conventional meat products. In plant-based meat analogues, some nutritional values are even superior to those of conventional meat products. For example, the products developed by PoH during the project are high in unsaturated fat from rapeseed oil which have shown positive effects on LDL cholesterol and a reduced risk of heart disease (Sacks et al., 2017). Additionally, yeast protein is considered a complete protein containing all nine essential amino acids and even contains a high amount of B vitamins. B12 specifically is known to be a nutrient lacking in a plant-based diet since its mainly found in animal based products (Pawlak et al., 2103). PoHs products, which are already on the market, have been fortified with B12 and other micronutrients to imitate the nutritional profile of animal-based products. This also helped to increase consumer acceptance but including B12 in a more natural way is more pleasing for the customer. Another reason showing the potential of consumer acceptability of yeast is the digestibility. Yeast protein is allergen free which gives it a big advantage compared to soy or gluten.

Apart from its nutritional benefits, the production of yeast protein is environmentally friendly, using less water and land than farming. It is also independent from climatic influences like drought, floodings and temperature changes since its growing vessel are fermenters. It is potentially possible to grow yeast protein globally.

The current scenario in Sweden is witnessing a notable escalation in meat prices, thereby narrowing the price disparity between plant-based and meat products. This trend presents a significant opportunity for plant-based products to experience an increase in sales, as consumers increasingly gravitate towards more cost-effective options during periods of inflation. The heightened demand for these products enables producers to leverage economies of scale, resulting in reduced production costs across various components, including raw materials, packaging, and overall production expenses. Simultaneously, this increased market traction facilitates greater investment in research and development endeavours aimed at enhancing the quality of ingredients employed in plant-based products. These advancements not only contribute to improving the sensory attributes such as mouthfeel and taste but also bolster the nutritional value of the offerings.

4.6 Literature review

The text above includes substantial number of findings from the literature. Below we just summarize the main aspects:

According to an extensive review by Onwezen et al. (2021), the important factors driving consumer acceptance of alternative proteins can be divided into three main domains: **product-related characteristics** (sensory acceptance, familiarity with the protein) (e.g. Circus & Robison, 2019; Michel et al., 2021; Verbeke, 2015) (Grahl et al, 2020; Weinrich & Elshiewy, 2019) , **psychological factors** (food neophobia or tendency to avoid novel foods, attachment to meat, food choice motives), and **external environment** (trust in food chain actors) such as trust and social environment (e.g. Siegrist & Hartmann, 2020).

In order to incorporate new protein sources into the human diet, consumer acceptance of these proteins or the foods made of them is crucial for long-term market success (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2020).

5 Results and discussions

5.1 Consumer trust

Elevated trust in food value chain stakeholders was found to play a significant role in convincing consumers to accept alternative proteins (Siegrist & Hartmann, 2020). Therefore, an own sub-chapter is dedicated for the consumer trust towards alternative proteins.

European regulatory framework for food (and feed to food-producing animals) has created conditions where food is produced safely and consumers can, in general, trust the safety of the food they eat. Findings in the large European consumer survey carried out in the project support the statement. The majority of European consumers do not have fears towards the use of alternative proteins in foods, i.e. they think that it is safe to eat food including alternative protein ingredients once the product has been accepted for markets (Arvola et al. 2021).

The findings of the survey, however, reveals that there are some countries in Europe (e.g. Germany, Poland, and the UK) where large groups of consumers express clear mistrust towards food industry and retail, in particular towards large business companies (Arvola et al, 2021).

In UK retail, most of the consumer trust is linked to trust in the brand. Consumers trust in the retailer to provide safe, responsibly sourced products across their own-label range. This is why product safety for example is not a marketable factor: it is a legitimate expectation of the consumer. However, there are some exceptions: food scandals or poor transparency about a product's ingredients will break consumer trust.

The mistrust found in the survey (Arvola et al., 2021) obviously arises from past incidences of food scandals in these countries where some food companies knowingly acted against the European food regulation. Although these scandals have been individual cases, they have had a strong negative impact for the whole field of business and many consumers still remember them.

Consumer trust was also studied in WP3. According to these studies, Icelanders seem to have more trust in value chain actors than Swedes and Germans. An additional scale from the publication by McCreedy et al (2020) was used to measure the trust in food industry. Consumers in Germany rated the properties that measure transparency and communication in the food industry less well. However, the results should only be evaluated as trends and are not significant. This could be an important signal for players in the German market that great importance should be attached to communication and transparency. This is of course to be considered in marketing campaigns for products with new alternative proteins.

In the UK (and in some other European countries as well) there is a movement away from artificial colours and flavours which is gaining traction: consumers want to see more natural products. This provides an opportunity for the alternative proteins, which although novel, are in themselves derived from natural elements. There is also an increasing awareness of ultra-processed foods and concerns by vegan consumers about whether these are healthy. Whilst they may be lower in fibre and higher in sugar, salt and fat than their processed counterparts, they are lower in saturated fats that are derived from animal ingredients. One particular issue

for ultra-processed vegan foods can be the low protein content when the product is marketed as a faux-meat product (e.g. jackfruit substitute for pulled pork).

Trust in the product is less likely to be an issue if it is sold under a retailers own-label and this would be an important vehicle to market for products utilising these alternative proteins. Furthermore, to gain consumer trust, where possible the use of these alternative proteins for food should avoid further ultra-processing, and where it is used, to call out the high protein and lower saturated fats content compared to the meats or dairy products they are substituting. It can also be useful to fortify the products: this has been an important marketable factor for plant-based milks and can be extended to foods where the alternative proteins are used as an animal protein substitute.

5.2 Consumer acceptance

From the literature we can learn that product-related characteristics (sensory acceptance, familiarity with the protein), psychological factors (food neophobia or tendency to avoid novel foods, attachment to meat, food choice motives), and external environment (trust in food chain actors) play important role in driving consumer acceptance of alternative proteins (Onwezen et al. (2021) and references therein). But factors influencing consumer acceptance and food choices go beyond that.

Insight data from the UK (Mintel, 2022) demonstrates that food and drink consumers value naturalness highly but that there is a trade-off between sustainability and naturally produced food and drink: purchases of sustainable food and drink would prefer a more sustainable, synthetically produced food or drink product over a less sustainable, naturally produced one (46%). This provides an opportunity for the alternative proteins by highlighting the sustainability credentials of the products (for example the circularity). In fact, the insight showed that the higher the interest in sustainability, the more open the consumer to synthetically produced food or drink products (66% of those who choose sustainable food or drink all or most of the time). Younger consumers (age 16-34) also are more open to such products, which aligns with their commitment to sustainability, and supports the findings from the National survey where younger age also predicted the membership of positive segment (and those with elevated health, environment and ethics motivation behind food choices), indicating that younger consumers are more open to alternative proteins. It is expected that this concept acceptance will continue as this generation ages, and thus the share of population who are open to this concept will increase over time.

In Europe, we have seen industry interest in using alternative proteins: in April 2021 Mars Petcare launched 'Lovebug' insect based dry cat food. The protein is 100% black soldier fly larvae (30% of the ingredients) produced on 100% surplus and wasted food, at a facility powered by renewable electricity. The Mars Lovebug marketing can be used as a model for the use of alternative proteins in feed: it is useful to note that the product is clearly labelled as 'insect based' on front of pack. Nutritional and digestibility factors are highlighted on pack, and supportive messaging on their website explains that the flies are treated humanely (the 5 freedoms: hunger, thirst, discomfort, pain, injury or disease, freedom to express normal behaviour, fear or distress). Furthermore, the packaging is plastic free and recyclable. In August 2022, a major UK supermarket chain (Morrisons) launched carbon neutral eggs produced from hens fed insects which are produced using waste from the supermarket's own

waste fruit and vegetables. This marketing validates the insight data referenced above that openness to synthetically produced food is linked to consumers who value sustainability.

However, it should be noted that Sustainability credentials are not sufficient enough to boost consumer confidence and turn it into a purchase on their own though. Alternative proteins must achieve taste, price and usability requirements: all of which outweigh sustainability in consumers' food and drink choices (Mintel. 2023). Plant milks are a good illustration of this: hemp and pea milk have struggled to succeed despite their sustainability credentials, compared to oat milk which have a more palatable flavour and usability innovation. This is an important consideration for the alternative proteins, when reflecting on the results of the consumer analysis on the salmon in the NextGenProteins project (see ch. 4.2.2. and Rubio et al., 2023).

From the perspective of a food company, plant-based protein sources need to be developed further. Now, the trend is to develop and produce products which imitate meat products, like sausages or steaks which come with the need of E numbers, like stabilizers, gelling agents and shelf-life extenders. Despite them being legal and highly controlled by the EU government, E numbers are viewed as unhealthy or even dangerous for consumption (van Gunst and Roodenburg, 2019). Additionally, it can be hard to develop a product that can imitate the texture and taste of their meat counterpart perfectly. If a consumer tries a vegan product, which does not fulfil their expectations, the consumer is less open to try another brand or product.

A positive first experience is highly important for the acceptance of novel food products by consumers. If the expectations are not filled, there may not be a second chance. Furthermore, it may not be enough that the novel product just fulfils the minimum expectations or is equal to a standard reference of consumers. The novel product may need to exceed the expectations and give some additional value for the consumer in order to convince the consumer in a way that leads to a purchasing decision, and not only once but over and over. The additional value may come from taste, nutritional properties, sustainability facts, price of the product, etc.

The findings from the consumer studies of WP5 (Arvola et al, 2021; Matullat et al. 2023) indicate that consumers should not be regarded as homogenous mass. Based on the acceptance measurements, four consumer segments for each alternative protein sources were identified and characterised. Consumers having neutral attitudes towards the considered proteins, were found to form the largest consumer segment for all ingredients. For Spirulina and Torula yeast, there are more positive than negative-minded consumers. Differences between the considered proteins could be found in their attitudinal background variables such as food choice motives, meat attachment, trust in food chain, and location. Familiarity with alternative and future proteins appear to be predictors for the positive-minded segments. Contrarily, a strong tendency to avoid food, a high desire for meat and a low trust in the food industry, are suggested to be predictors for the negative segments. A consumer segment with highly positive perceptions could be identified for Spirulina and Torula, showing market potential for food products including these ingredients.

5.3 Approaches to boost consumer trust and acceptability

5.3.1 Research perspectives

According to the results of consumer studies done in the project, trust seems not to be a big barrier for consumer acceptance of alternative proteins. Low trust correlates with negative perceptions towards alternative proteins and their use in food, but not with other consumer segments. As the consumer segment with clearly negative perceptions represented a clear minority for all the considered alternative proteins, approaches to boost consumer acceptance could be focused to consumers having positive or neutral perceptions towards alternative proteins and turning their attitudes to real behaviour. Accordingly, focus could be in the other factors affecting the acceptance rather than trust.

The study results are in line with the recent evidence that European consumers' attitudes towards alternative proteins are becoming more positive. However, the attitudes are not yet translated into actual consumption choices. Therefore, it is suggested that interventions should be made to convert the attitudes into behaviours. For example, as younger consumers seem to be more interested in alternative proteins, digital tools and social media platforms such as Instagram or TikTok could be used to reach the target group. Especially in the area of food, Instagram is a powerful tool to present and inform about new products. It could be possible to cooperate with influencers who have a wide social reach and who are already popular in non-food or even food sector.

5.3.2 Retailer perspectives

As insight studies have shown, and the salmon consumer testing proved, achieving key sensory attributes (particularly flavour, texture) are the most important path to consumer acceptance. Furthermore, UK insight data illustrates that a key to boosting consumer acceptance is by promoting the sustainability credentials of the product: half of the participants in a study (MINTEL, 2022) agreed with the statement that "an unusual ingredient being sustainable would make me willing to try food/drinks containing it (e.g., bread with seaweed, or burger patties with insect fed beef). As with the data regarding openness to a synthetically produced product, agreement with this statement increases to 68% for consumers who choose sustainable food and drink most or all of the time. Equally, this statement resonates with younger age groups (61% for under 45-year category). Further, a study on plant-based market opportunities (Mintel 2023) showed that 42% of people felt information on environmental impact would make meat substitutes more appealing.

Therefore, the appropriate target market is likely to be generation Z and millennials (ages 16-34), and in future generation Alpha, and those with a keen interest in sustainability who buy sustainable food and drink most or all of the time. Marketing must highlight the green credentials of the product and not shy away from the fact it may not be viewed as natural since data suggests sustainability overrides naturalness. Consumers who are following a high protein diet (for example body building) could also be a target market for some of these alternative proteins, if the protein content of the product were highlighted and the format of the product was suitably convenient.

Promoting sustainability could also open up the market for alternative proteins to be used in vegan meat substitute products, with insight showing that information on environmental

impacts would make meat substitute products more appealing to potential vegan meat substitute consumers (MINTEL, 2022).

Insight data suggests promotions of food produced with alternative ingredients will boost consumer confidence to purchase them: 75% of a pool of internet users who choose food/drink products with sustainability claims agreed with the statement that promotions on food & drink would encourage them to buy products they normally would not buy (MINTEL 2023). Indeed, this is the most common vehicle to introducing new products in retail.

A potential barrier that needs to be overcome in the short term is the impact of global economics at this point in time: 65% of participants (Mintel 2023) agreed with the statement that “the rising cost of living will make sustainability of food and drink less important to me”. Interestingly, one study (Mintel 2022) showed that the majority (52%) of red meat/poultry eaters say they would buy meat substitutes that are cheaper than meat so this provides an opportunity for the alternative proteins in vegetarian/vegan meals if they can be competitively priced during this economic downturn. Once pressures on household incomes ease, the long-term predicted focus on sustainability is likely to regain momentum, fuelling meat substitute consumption growth and making meat substitute products a more accessible alternative. (Mintel, 2022).

Products do not need to be offered at the lowest price point to gain penetration with consumers. If their perceived value should be high, then consumers are often willing to purchase them over cheaper products i.e. the concept “you get what you pay for”. Thus, consumers who value sustainability and are more likely to purchase these alternative protein products, are more willing to pay more for them if they believe they are getting good value.

Marketing is critical here to communicate the value of the product. This marketing can take many forms and the most important messages should be communicated on pack and as explained above, the high sustainability and animal welfare credentials are probably the most useful factors to highlight here. However, marketing in other ways can support general acceptance: posters in stores which provide a little more detail than can fit on a pack, articles in the media that go into depth about how the products are derived, why they are sustainable will all assist with acceptance.

Social media influencers could have an integral role in creating a food trend for the target consumers, given the type of consumer most willing to be accepting of these products. With over half of the world on social media (Datreportal, 2022) they are able to find new products through this platform. In fact, these platforms can compete with traditional search methods such as google, with almost 40% of Gen Z choosing Instagram and TikTok over google (Shopify 2023). Such influencers offer a cost-effective approach to marketing Credible personal finance. Given the current climate of inflation and more focus on ethical products, influencers who are known to create budget recipes, zero waste strategies and provide finance expertise play an important role in supporting consumers consider the product in this context (Xeim 2023). The influencers do not have to be celebrities: micro influencers can also be useful in generating awareness of a product. There is also the potential for virtual influencers and avatars, which are expected to increase with time, and which will resonate more with Gen Z and Alpha consumers who will have had an awareness of these from an early age and likely to be more responsive to them. This approach must be taken with caution though, as there has been backlash to avatars that do not represent diversity and the values of the brand using

them (Xeim 2023). As social media favours video content and with platforms recently enabling the use of longer video content, it provides an opportunity for a more authentic engagement with the consumer: research indicates that it can result in better brand recognition and conversion due to the storytelling and with many consumers wanting to see product videos before purchase (Xeim 2023). Social media intelligence platforms offer the opportunity to gather data on followers and understand their interests to deliver targeted influencer campaigns (Xeim 2023).

Since insight shows that because openness to alternative ingredients is strong with younger consumers, it is likely to endure, and they will represent a larger share of the market: this validates investment opportunities and longevity of these ingredients for companies looking to explore alternative proteins.

5.3.3 Food company perspectives

For a food company it is necessary to improve products on a regular basis to increase consumer acceptance. The goal is to achieve a product that requires less E-numbers while at the same time improving texture and taste. This development is usually connected to an increase in raw material cost which is also unwanted by the customer. Therefore, companies like Peas of Heaven must make the right decisions and be open to change formulas if the overall view on products change.

The next step is to get the customer familiar with the product. The positive aspects need to be highlighted and advantages compared to a previous version of the same product or to another product. Nowadays it's common to use social media platforms like Instagram or TikTok to advertise new products. Apart from having an own brand account, it is helpful to collaborate with influencers which are known by food related content. They are perceived as experts in this field. Their opinion counts more than the opinion of the producer of the product.

PoH focuses a lot on availability and normalization. The price is comparable to the ones of meat products and some stores place products of PoH directly next to the meat products. The likelihood of purchasing the vegan option is higher when consumers can directly compare the plant-based option. Sales increased by 40% after moving the products from the vegan shelf to the meat shelf. Availability also means the option to buy the product in as many places as possible. PoH products are in all major supermarkets in Sweden and in convenience stores and gas stations.

New protein sources need to become as normal as conventional protein sources. They are expected to provide the same or better nutritional value with a similar or cheaper price. Taste and choice of products needs to be on the same level as meat products to convince the end customer to change their current behaviour.

6 Conclusions

Conclusions of the work are given as NextGenProteins recommendations to boost consumer acceptance towards alternative proteins and their use in foods. The recommendations below are based on the prioritization of approaches discussed in the report.

6.1 Products must be price competitive

Pricing of food products including those consisting of or containing alternative protein ingredients must be competitively set against conventional proteins to encourage trial and subsequently build acceptance. Preferably the price should be lower than the corresponding product containing meat protein. If this is not the case, the product must contain additional benefits for the customer.

6.2 Promote sustainability

Consumers are increasingly aware of the impact of intensive farming to the environment. This awareness should be turned into personal food choices by feeding scientific information about the sustainability of food products including that of alternative proteins.

6.3 Promote food products

The best way to overcome suspicions towards new food products is to try them. Therefore, any kind of promotion of alternative protein products should be considered to increase consumer acceptance for the food products. This would include tastings in supermarkets, introductory offers, etc. in order to get consumers to try the product.

6.4 Continue development of products

Ideally, range and choice of food products should be as wide as possible to meet the varied preferences of consumers. However, this will be limited by the commercial nature of food retailing, with each individual product having to earn the space afforded to it. Food companies should continue the development of new food products including alternative proteins. Part of the new products should go beyond typical categories of meat alternatives to attract consumers that are omnivore but who are suspicious of meat alternatives. In addition to increase the range of products, the food development should focus on decreasing the number of E-labels in products, keeping in mind the importance of taste and other sensory properties in the acceptance of new products.

6.5 Marketing through social media influencers

The most potential users of food including alternative proteins are also active users of social media. Therefore, marketing of alternative protein food products should take place through influencers in social media. Currently Instagram and TikTok are the best suited platforms to reach the target groups. The marketing should underline the value of products.

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